

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The commonest is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Will be darkish or light brown (cinnamon), typically even white. Not always black in colour. 900,000 and not threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear can be discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Size: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six feet in length. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare events. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are some of the very best at climbing timber. Their comparatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb timber for safety, food, and even hibernation. The majority of their weight loss program is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Diet: Their assorted weight loss program provides them the power to reside in a big vary of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They're the most definitely bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are essentially the most widespread of all bear species, discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are accountable for almost all bear assaults in North America, with forty six per year. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and diminished habitat make lots of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a large variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the tips, which led to the title of essentially the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt young mammals comparable to elk and moose. Their color varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are discovered in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 ft long, and have a shoulder peak of 3.3 ft. □□ Weight loss plan: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies are typically bigger than these found in the Rocky Mountains because of a richer weight loss program. Every year there are 46 assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Known for his or her aggressive habits, grizzlies are answerable for the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Dimension: Kodiak bears are virtually as massive as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 ft long, and four ft tall on the shoulder. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their weight loss program is just like mainland grizzly bears. Nonetheless, as a result of more plentiful meals sources, the islands can support a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to change into their very own subspecies. This has led to a more complex social structure which results in much less conflict between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears might be aggressive. On account of their isolation, there is only one attack on people each different yr. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss program is generally made up of meat, usually from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white but is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range in the snow-coated arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and might be 7 to 10 feet tall. They're a threatened species due to loss of habitat from climate change. Despite their huge dimension polar bears could be quick, maintaining a 6 mph pace within the water. □□ Options: Compared to different bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, slim head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Weight loss plan: Their weight loss program consists principally of animals, particularly seals which they can scent from a mile away. Although they seem white, their fur is definitely clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears will be extremely dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Attacks are rare as a result of distant nature of their habitat. Known for its cream color chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Simple to tame and sometimes widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account weak. □□ Size: One of many smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to 75 inches tall. □□ Food plan: Depending on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on people are growing as

individuals encroach on their habitat. □□ Harmful? They are certainly one of the easiest bears to tame (and subsequently widespread in circuses), but Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found only in China. 99% of its diet is bamboo. The truth is, the second individual in historical past to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas protecting his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are found only in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 stay in the wild and they're thought-about a weak species. □□ Dimension: Pandas weigh around 300 pounds and can be over four feet tall, a powerful feat considering they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at birth. It additionally has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in gentle brown and white. □□ Weight-reduction plan: In contrast to different bears the panda's weight loss program is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Features: The giant panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them regular: they poop over 40 times a day! □□ Harmful? Assaults are uncommon however harmful, provided that pandas have one among the highest bite forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Solar bear is found in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It is the least studied bear and. Its population is uncertain however considered weak and on the decline due to loss of habitat and poaching. Sun bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and different physique components used in traditional medicines. □□ Dimension: They stand solely 39 to 55 inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Options: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for their pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that looks like a rising solar. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Solar bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." The truth is, they've an incredibly long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Harmful? As a result of its shy nature, assaults are rare. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the title sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is discovered in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of less than 20,000, they're thought-about susceptible. □□ Dimension: They are 55 to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Features: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they're simple to tell aside from different Asiatic bears. In reality, they are very fast and might out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the wrong way up from bushes. They are noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their huge curved claws. □□ Food regimen: [small teddy bear online](#)

Their eating regimen consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Dangerous? They are one of the vital aggressive bears, with the most attacks on people, principally resulting from shock encounters. They blow the mud around with huge puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they are often heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not combine nicely with rhinos and elephants, typically charging at each other when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's last short-confronted bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that look like glasses. This vulnerable species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Dimension: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing forty seven to 79 inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's final quick-confronted bear and the only bear native to South America. □□ Features: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that sometimes appear to be glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes the place they build nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses. □□ Food plan: Spectacled bears are principally herbivores with a eating regimen consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they may opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Dangerous? Residing in remote mountains, these shy bears could be the least harmful of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears however bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear behavior is nearer to the polar bear. They characteristic the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably on the London Zoo in 1859, however have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA tests were unable to find out what type of bear it was. Adorable koalas should not bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in area. Most bear assaults happen when a bear is startled or

defending their cubs. Crimson pandas? They're in their very own household that are nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears.

1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks that may indicate a bear is close by, in which case you want to be further vigilant. Listed below are a few ideas you should utilize to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe.
2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're right here so they do not by chance startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack.
3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** Whereas you will have nice intentions, a bear is prone to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself.
3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Gadgets (AT CAMP).** In case you see a bear, do not try to approach or feed it. This contains meals, but also your toiletries, for example. Whichever methodology you select, make sure that it is at the least 200 toes away from your tent so you don't attract bears to your campsite.
4. **Keep CALM.** In the event you meet a bear, do not run. Try to make yourself look as huge as attainable, waving your arms above your head. You may as well extend a jacket above your head to make your self look bigger. Lock these items in a bear canister or use a bear bag to dangle them up in a tree. Don't scream or attempt to scare the bear.
5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Converse to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 toes) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward.
6. **Battle Again.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, do not play dead. Which bear is the biggest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 toes long, and 4.0 to 5.25 toes tall, the largest bear by both measurement and weight is the polar bear. The most important ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Combat again with all your energy and hope that it'll again down. Which bear is the most dangerous? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is known for the most assaults. When in bear nation, it's always sensible to hold bear spray. It's well deserved, especially when cubs are around. Every year there are approximately 46 grizzly attacks, 6 leading to death. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome status. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most likely to see an American black bear, on common there is only one attack per yr. In terms of raw chunk energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are strong and to not be messed with. When using the bite force quotient (chunk power relative to dimension), the sun bear packs probably the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the fire but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he grew to become an icon and to today is the star of the longest-working public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear known for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired countless through-hikers to try to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a responsibility-free life-style. He also might be the first bear to obtain his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son usually would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada near the place he was from. Chris additionally wrote Learn how to Hike the Appalachian Path. Equal parts backpacking food and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic tips, guides and the way-to's in your inbox each two weeks.

